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Analysis of the method of increasing the service life of belt conveyor rollers

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Abstract: Conveyor transport is a type of multi-purpose transport. Conveyor transport is part of the heavy starting mechanism, which is part of electromechanical equipment. In the automation of conveyor transport, the main working device is a feedback sensor. if we compare the indicators of the thyristor converter system and the electromechanical system, then it can be seen that the energy efficient indicators are higher in the thyristor device. Conveyor transport has moments of resistance to electric current. these include: the working mechanism, the moment of resistance created by friction and the moment of resistance depending on the mass of the load when the load is loaded. The dynamic moment is the moment showing the greatest resistance to the movement of conveyor transport.

Key words: Roller. support tape. Frequency. Feedback sensor

Анализ способа увеличения срока службы роликов ленточных конвейеров

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Аннотация: Конвейерный транспорт – это вид многоцелевого транспорта. Конвейерный транспорт является частью тяжелого пускового механизма, входящего в состав электромеханического оборудования. В автоматизации конвейерного транспорта основным рабочим устройством является датчик обратной связи. Если сравнить показатели системы тиристорного преобразователя и электромеханической системы, то видно, что показатели энергоэффективности выше у тиристорного устройства. Конвейерный транспорт имеет моменты сопротивления электрическому току. к ним относятся: рабочий механизм, момент сопротивления, создаваемый трением и момент сопротивления, зависящий от массы груза при нагружении груза. Динамическим моментом является момент, оказывающий наибольшее сопротивление движению конвейерного транспорта.

Ключевые слова: Ролик. поддерживающая лента. Частота. Датчик обратной связи

Roller supports) are one of the most important parts of the conveyor. The resistance to belt movement and the service life of the belt are directly related to their condition. In the loaded (working) station of the conveyor, the roller supports for the flat belt consist of one roller, and to give the belt a tube shape - three (in some cases, two or five) rollers are installed, which are located at a certain angle relative to each other in the vertical plane. Will cry.

One roller support is always installed in the unload station of the conveyor. In order to limit the hanging of the belt between the rollers, to ensure smooth movement, to prevent material spillage from the belt, and to increase the service life of the belt, the distance between the rollers is $1.0 \div 1.4$ m in the loaded station, and 2 times more in the unloaded station.

Figure 1: Dependence of productivity on the angle of inclination of side rollers

In most underground conveyors, the side rollers are installed at a 200 degree angle. As can be seen from the figure 2.17, the belt productivity has a maximum value when the angle of inclination of the side rollers is 40-45. Therefore, in some constructions of conveyors, side rollers are installed at a slope of 300, where the productivity increases by 13-15% compared to a slope of 200. It is currently not advisable to increase the angle of inclination of the side rollers more than (300), because there is a risk of its breakage when the tape is placed on the rollers. The main reasons for the failure of rollers

- High pressure on the bearing;
- Impact of the roller axle
- Impact of the roller axle:
- Contamination of the bearing;
- Not standing on the same balance;

Roller wear and corrosion The cost of rollers is a major part of the total cost of transporting goods with a belt conveyor. One of the reasons for the rapid failure of rollers is that due to contamination of the bearing joints, they stop rotating.

Figure 2: Equipment for collecting dust falling on rollers

1. Belt conveyor frame, 2. Working roller, 3. Belt, 4. Pulling drum, 5. Bottom roller, 6. Dust driving equipment base, 7. Dust driving pipe, 8. Belt fixing roller, 9. Tensioning device, 10. Tensioning drum, 11. Bunker, 12. Dust removal equipment.

By avoiding the dust coming to the belt conveyor rollers through this created equipment, we will be able to reduce the stiffness of the rollers, i.e. they stop without rotating, by 7%. The principle of operation of the newly created equipment is carried out in the following sequence. Air comes to the pipes 3 designed to drive the dust coming to the rollers, and with the help of the compressor 2, which drives the compressed air. The start of the compressor is carried out with the help of an electric motor attached to one axle. The electric motor connected to 220 V voltage rotates the compressor blades together with it, as a result of which the compressor begins to send compressed air through the drive pipe through the pipe designed to clean the rollers from dust. Compressed air coming under pressure blows the dust from the bearing caps into the air.

There are also several types of conveyors, such as belt conveyors, shovel conveyors, and plate conveyors. Conveyors of this type once again prove the effectiveness of using conveyor transport in various conditions of production and mining industry. Belt conveyors are widely used in manufacturing and industrial enterprises.

Belt conveyors are more efficient than other types of conveyors in terms of efficiency and construction.

Asynchronous electric machines are mainly used as electric drives of belt conveyors. For belt conveyors with low power and located horizontally, it is advisable to use mainly short-circuit rotor asynchronous motors, and for conveyors with a large power and a certain slope, it is advisable to use phase rotor asynchronous motors.

The reason for this is that the start of the conveyor electric drive in a certain inclined position requires a slightly larger starting torque and a smooth start. For this reason, phased rotor asynchronous motors are installed in conveyor transports of large capacity and inclined position in order to ensure smooth start-up during start-up. In other cases, it is advisable to use asynchronous machines with short-circuited rotors, which are inexpensive and have a simple structural structure.

As the length of the conveyor transport increases, it becomes more difficult to carry out work and control along the full length of the conveyor. On supply conveyors, there are often cases of non-continuity of cargo supply during cargo transportation. In this case, the conveyor's operation and efficiency decrease over a period of time, and the equipment consumes excessive energy. Conveyor transport requires the use of a large-capacity electric conveyor for a long length, and the energy consumption of a large-capacity electric conveyor during operation is also significantly large.

During idle operation, the useful efficiency of the conveyor transport is zero percent, therefore, the electricity consumed at this time is completely wasted energy. To eliminate this situation, it is advisable to stop the conveyor transport when there is no load and restart it when the load arrives.

But manual management of this process is somewhat complicated and causes inconvenience, therefore, automatic implementation of this process is convenient in every way and a factor in easing the human effort. We will consider several optimal options for monitoring and controlling the conveyor idle.

As an initial solution, we can control whether the conveyor is loaded or unloaded by means of light sensing sensors. In this process, two light sensing sensors are installed at the beginning and end of the length of the conveyor. After the light sensing sensor located in the loading part receives the information signal that the last load has passed, the light sensing sensor located in the head part of the conveyor is activated, and the last load is detected by the conveyor. gives the information signal that it has passed the head part to the time relay, counts the time interval set in the time relay memory and sends the shutdown signal to the control panel of the conveyor during this time interval.

If the arrival of the load is interrupted for a certain reason and falls on the conveyor before the time relay is disconnected, the time relay and light detection sensor cancel the conveyor shutdown information and return to the initial control state.

Also, the signal transmission process is stopped even if the load supply is restored in the time interval from the time when the first light sensor gives a signal

until the second light sensor gives a signal. In this way, the control of the conveyor depends on the type of cargo it carries, and also directly depends on the environment in which the conveyor is used.

When the optical sensor has a high dust content, high temperature and high humidity are more likely to give false information, so using an optical sensor for these situations is an unreliable solution. In closed construction and dust-free conditions, light sensing sensors allow to achieve great efficiency and great economic savings.

As a second option for the control of the conveyor in the unloaded state, we can include the implementation by means of load control devices or weight control sensors on the conveyor. Weight control sensors are an electrical device that implements the switching process and gives a signal due to the weight change occurring in a certain volume or in a moving structure.

In the control of conveyor transport with the help of weight sensors, sensitivity and process control is performed by determining the difference in the weight of the loaded and unloaded state. After the weight sensors give the information signal that the conveyor is fully unloaded, the time relay starts counting the control time.

The purpose of setting the control time is to ensure that the conveyor does not stop when the supply of the load is interrupted for a certain period of time due to the occurrence of various situations in the supply of the conveyor. The fields of application of weight sensors are very wide and they serve effectively even in dusty environment and high temperature environment. We can cite its high cost as a disadvantage of weight sensors.

In the above case, elimination of excessive energy consumption of the conveyor during idle operation on the conveyor allows to achieve great efficiency. As an example, we can cite the fact that in the process of ore supply to beneficiation factories, ores are transported to the crusher using electric locomotive dump trucks.

After one locomotive has finished unloading, a certain amount of time elapses before the second locomotive arrives and maneuvers it for the unloader, while the crusher's supply conveyors run unloaded. With the help of the above-mentioned control sensors, it will be possible to realize the full automatic mode of operation of the conveyor.

In addition to increasing the energy efficiency of conveyor transport, it is necessary to ensure that its technical parameters do not change and do not exceed the norm. In this case, we will see in the experiment that the temperature of the

engine winding, the active power coefficient, the magnetic lines of force, the currents in the transient process of the stator are normal. One of the most important parameters of the electric drive of conveyor transport is its temperature.

Figure 3: Electric motor stator winding temperature graph

During the operation of electrical circuits, a part of the energy is used to compensate for their losses. All types of energy waste are converted into heat, mainly increasing the temperature of the active parts of electrical circuits, and a part of it is transferred to the environment.

The temperature has a negative effect on the insulation of the pipe, reducing the duration of operation of the electrical circuit.

During the operation of electrical circuits, a part of the energy is used to compensate for their losses. All types of energy waste are converted into heat, mainly increasing the temperature of the active parts of electrical circuits, and a part of it is transferred to the environment. It consists of a complex of electrical conductors, magnetic conductor elements and structural details. These parts have different thermal conductivity, heat capacity and cooling conditions. This shows that the heat field distribution of electric currents is complex in nature.

Figure 4: Operating diagram of an electric motor

Improving the efficiency of electric energy by saving in the electrical management of conveyor transport. During idle operation, the useful efficiency of the conveyor transport is zero percent, therefore, the electricity consumed at this time is completely wasted energy.

To eliminate this situation, it is advisable to stop the conveyor transport when there is no load and restart it when the load arrives. This prevents the reactive power from exceeding the norm by restricting the operation of the conveyor transport in the idle mode. At the same time, we will have the opportunity to save from the loss of high-power electricity in the network and the energy consumed by conveyor transport.

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